

Approach to the Management and Treatment of Women With Dysmenorrhea

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Abstract: The presence of persistent pain syndrome leads to disorders of mental and physical health, being the cause of temporary and persistent loss of working capacity. Purpose of the study: assessment of pain syndrome and psychoemotional state of women suffering from algodysmenorrhea. The examined were divided into groups: in the 1st group the treatment with NSAIDs was carried out, in the 2nd group NSAIDs and combined oral contraceptives were used. And so, pelvic pain syndrome is represented by gynecologic pathology with a small morphofunctional manifestation, autonomic disturbance and psychoemotional disorder. The main principle of dysmenorrhea treatment is aimed at normalization of menstrual cycle and reduction of prostaglandins production, and the treatment should be personalized.

Keywords: algodysmenorrhea, chronic pelvic pain syndrome, combined oral contraceptives, nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs.

Introduction. Pelvic pain, as a symptom inherent in most gynecologic diseases, is the most common complaint. Pelvic pain is a common physical suffering, causes significant material and moral damage to women and represents a medical and social problem. The presence of persistent pain syndrome leads to mental and physical health disorders, being the cause of temporary and permanent disability [1,4,10].

In medical practice, the manifestation of pelvic pain with its consequences is considered as chronic pelvic pain syndrome (CPPS) [5,7]. Painful menstruation in the international classification of diseases is coded by the term “algodysmenorrhea”, implying menstrual painfulness that is not organic in nature. This cyclic pathological process is characterized by the appearance of the days of menstruation pronounced pain in the lower abdomen, which may be accompanied by severe general weakness, nausea, vomiting, headache, dizziness, lack of appetite, increased body temperature to 37-38 C0, chills, dry mouth, abdominal bloating, a feeling of “cotton” feet, fainting and other emotional and autonomic disorders. Sometimes the leading symptom may be one of the above complaints, which bothers the patient more than the pain. Severe pain exhausts the nervous system, contributes to the development of asthenic state, and reduces memory and performance [2, 11].

Purpose of the study: assessment of pain syndrome and psycho-emotional state of women suffering from algodysmenorrhea.

Materials and methods: At the first stage of the study, we conducted a comprehensive examination of 80 women who applied to the Women's Health Center at the TMA clinic. The examination included anamnesis collection, general clinical, gynecological examinations, ultrasound examination. After the above complex examination, 60 women suffering from algodysmenorrhea, aged 22 to 38 years (average age 30 years), remained under our observation. All the examined were divided into two groups: 1st - 30 women who were treated with non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, 2nd - 30 women who were

prescribed oral contraceptive - Belara - from 1 to 7 days of menstrual cycle after treatment with NSAIDs.

In group 1, we considered it advisable to use the drug Celebrex, since both selective COX-2 inhibitors and non-selective drugs (COX-1 and COX-2 inhibitors) can be used from the NSAID group. Selective drugs have an undoubted advantage, which, to a much lesser extent than non-selective drugs, inhibit the synthesis of gastroprotective Pg, which means they pose a much lower risk of developing gastralgia, erosive and ulcerative lesions of the gastrointestinal tract. It is among them that celecoxib (Celebrex), which provides persistent analgesia, belongs. In the first days of the appearance of pain - 400 mg at a time, in the following days - a single dose during the day - 200 mg. It should also be noted such an advantage of celecoxib as the absence of an effect on bleeding time and blood clotting. As a result, taking this drug did not lead to increased menstrual discharge [3,9,11].

In group 2, to the above therapy, from the 5th day of menstruation, we added the drug Belara - a low-dose monophasic estrogen-gestagenic contraceptive (Gedeon-Richter, Hungary), which contains 30 micrograms of ethinyl estradiol and chlormadinone acetate. When using a combined oral contraceptive (COC), there is a decrease in the secretion of follicle-stimulating and luteinizing hormone, inhibition of ovulation, secretory transformation and endometrial proliferation. In addition, when taking the drug Belara, the properties of cervical mucus change, which leads to a decrease in the penetration of sperm into the uterus through the cervical canal. Chlormadinone acetate is a progestogenic component with antiandrogenic properties. The mechanism of action of chlormadinone is related to its ability to competitively replace androgenic hormones at specific receptors, reducing the severity of the effects of exogenous and endogenous androgens. Chlormadinone acetate has an antiminerlocorticoid effect and is able to prevent weight gain and the appearance of other symptoms (for example, edema) associated with estrogen-dependent fluid retention. By influencing the antiandrogenic activity, it helps to reduce acne, oily skin and hair. This effect of chlormadinone acetate is similar to the action of natural progesterone produced by the female body. We took this into account when choosing a contraceptive, especially for women with hormone-dependent fluid retention - overweight, as well as women with acne and seborrhea. The tablets were taken every day at about the same time, washed down with a small amount of liquid, in the sequence indicated on the blister pack, 1 tablet per day for 21 consecutive days, followed by a 7-day interval in taking tablets [6,9,10].

The effectiveness of treatment was assessed based on complaints and clinical and laboratory data. The examination included a questionnaire specially developed by us, which reflects both qualitative and quantitative characteristics of pain. The intensity of these symptoms was estimated in points (from 0 to 3). The total score was a pain index. Psychoemotional testing was conducted by determining reactive and personal anxiety on the Spielberg-Hanin scale.

The severity of the pain syndrome was assessed using a visual analog scale (VAS), which is a ruler, on one side of which a rectangle with a length of 100 mm is applied, colored in an increasing color scheme (from white to black). The white color corresponds to the inscription "no pain", and the black color corresponds to "maximum pain". The degree of pain intensity is determined by analogy with the change in color saturation by moving the cursor indicating the numerical index of the severity of pain on a horizontal scale with a length of 100 mm located on the back of the ruler. Visually, the analog scale is a fairly simple and non-invasive method that allows you to quickly assess the intensity of pain symptoms and the effectiveness of therapy. Pain assessment by VAS (100 mm) was performed before the start of therapy and in dynamics after treatment. In the dynamics of treatment, the patient herself recorded a numerical pain index in her protocol. In addition, the patients noted the effectiveness of therapy on a 4-point scale (0 – no pain, 1- insignificant, 2-satisfactory, 3-good, 4-excellent effect).

Results and discussion.

The duration of dysmenorrhea in the women under our supervision was: For 2 years, 30 (50%), 5 years – 20 (33.3%), more than 5 years – 10 (16.6%). Relapses during menstruation were noted by 37 (61.6%). There were no pregnancies in 15 (25%) patients, one birth in 20 (33.3%), two and three births in 25 (41.6%). 23% (38.3) of women suffered from miscarriage, with spontaneous miscarriage occurring in

14%, late miscarriages in 7%, and premature birth in 7%. The study of gynecological morbidity showed that 55% of the patients suffered from inflammatory diseases of the appendages. Chronic endometritis 47%, cervicitis 17%, colpitis 21%, infertility 13%.

The main complaints were severe pain in the lower back and lower abdomen 2-3 days before and during menstruation. Menstrual irregularities were observed in more than half of the women. Thus, hyperpolymenorrhea was present in 50% of the examined patients, oligomenorrhea in 19%.

The analysis of the questionnaires showed that the main complaints are pain in the lower abdomen and lower back: 17% regarded the pain as minor, 30% as severe, 53% of women as moderate. On the Spielberg-Hanin scale, more than half of the women had high levels of reactive and personal anxiety. Obviously, this was due to the nature of the pain. It should be noted that 25% of women have vegetative disorders. Thus, the pain syndrome was accompanied by headaches in 30%, swelling in 19.7%, palpitations in 10.6%.

When evaluating the effectiveness of pain on the VAS scale, the baseline level was 82 mm. Against the background of therapy during 3 menstrual cycles, in group 2, this indicator decreased to 10 mm, after a monthly course (NSAIDs on menstruation days), followed by the appointment of a combined oral contraceptive from the 5th day of menstruation.

The high effect of the treatment was found in 92% of women of the 2nd group (3.8 points) and in 88% of the 1st group (3.2 points). Of these, 88.7% of patients in the 2nd and 75.6% in the 1st group did not experience any pain. The remaining women, 3.7% and 12.4%, respectively, of the 2nd and 1st groups, felt minor discomfort.

So, as we can see, the main means of treating primary dysmenorrhea are oral contraceptives and nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs.

The oral contraceptive we have chosen reduces the volume of menstrual secretions by inhibiting endometrial proliferation and suppressing ovulation. Under conditions of anovulation, prostaglandin (PG) secretion by the endometrium decreases. The COC causes a decrease in the threshold of excitability of the smooth muscle cell and reduces its contractile activity, thereby contributing to a decrease in intrauterine pressure, frequency and amplitude of contractions of the uterine muscle. Increased contractile activity of the uterus may be the result of an increase in the concentration of estrogens in the luteal phase of the cycle. Estrogen can stimulate the release of PG-F2a and vasopressin. The use of combined estrogen-progestogen containing monophasic contraceptives leads to a decrease in the concentration of estrogens, and hence PG, and the disappearance or decrease in the severity of symptoms of dysmenorrhea. In addition, chlormadinone acetate contained in the drug has an antimineralocorticoid effect and is able to prevent weight gain and the appearance of other symptoms (for example, edema) associated with estrogen-dependent fluid retention. Chlormadinone acetate also has antiandrogenic activity and helps to reduce acne, oily skin and hair [6,8,10]. In the presence of various disorders of the reproductive system in the form of, first of all, menstrual function disorders, adequate hormonal therapy allows for correction of existing disorders.

NSAIDs may be used for women suffering from algodismenorrhea. Selective drugs have an undoubted advantage, among them is celecoxib, which provides persistent analgesia, and the absence of influence on bleeding time and blood clotting.

Conclusion.

Thus, summarizing the above, it should be concluded: pelvic pain syndrome is represented by gynecological pathology with a small morphofunctional manifestation, vegetative disorder and psychoemotional disorder. The main principle of dysmenorrhea treatment is pharmacotherapy aimed at normalizing the menstrual cycle and reducing prostaglandin production. In this case, treatment should be strictly individual, depending on the identified characteristics of the female body.

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